

EarlyCause

Causative mechanisms & integrative models linking early-life-stress to psycho-cardio-metabolic multi-morbidity

Deliverable D2.2

Data Coordination Centre

Reference	D2.2_ EarlyCause_EMBL_31082020
Lead Beneficiary	EMBL
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Dissemination level	Public
Type	Other
Official Delivery Date	31/08/2020
Date of validation of the WP leader	19/08/2020
Date of validation by the Project Coordinator	19/08/2020
Project Coordinator Signature	

EarlyCause is funded by the European Union's H2020 Framework
Under Grant Agreement 848158

Version log

Issue Date	Version	Involved	Comments
17/08/2020	V1	Alisha Ahamed & Jeena Rajan	1 st draft
18/08/2020	V2	Katharina Heil, Karim Lekadir	Comments on 1 st draft
19/08/2020	V3	Alisha Ahamed	Review comments and update
19/08/2020	Final	Katharina Heil, Karim Lekadir	Final, approved version

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable explains the function and features of the Data Coordination Centre (DCC) with regard to the EarlyCause project and outlines various methods for project partners to store, access and analyse data. The ultimate aim is to build a centralised research platform using the existing ELIXIR¹ infrastructure to enable integration and management of multi-dimensional data, thus allowing a rich search and browse environment for the discovery and selection of appropriate data sets with relevant project protocols for further exploration of causative mechanisms and molecular pathways linking early life stress (ELS) to psycho-cardiometabolic multi-morbidity. The DCC will provide comprehensive support to project partners, as well as a foundation to be sustained beyond the term of the project to support ongoing research in this important domain.

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2 Data Coordination Centre

With rapid advances and developments in sequencing technologies and life-science research, comes an increasingly wider range of data and data types. The data coordination centre (DCC) provides a technical infrastructure through which data can be shared, securely managed and integrated. Data sets will be made available to the Consortium partners initially, and eventually to the wider scientific community on a larger scale. The DCC consists of a technical platform, which will be easily accessible to users to upload or access data and experimental models relevant to early life stress (ELS) and their links, if any, with psycho-cardio-metabolic (PCM) multi or co-morbidities. All data generated will be associated with high quality metadata ensuring it adheres to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable) principles².

2.1 DCC Design

The DCC has been designed in such a way to utilise the data hub/portal software framework that was developed at EMBL-EBI for the COMPARE³ project. Data hubs facilitate the upload, manipulation and access of different data types through a single data portal. Several tools and interfaces that enable user workflow surround the system, providing a single platform for users who intend to make use of the DCC. A dedicated project email address, ena-earlycause@ebi.ac.uk, has been set up to provide assistance for any user queries.

Standards will be developed, together with project partners, to ensure high quality metadata is associated with all data produced. The DCC will ensure this information is captured through the incorporation of new sample checklists for standards reporting.

2.2 ELIXIR Core and Deposition Databases

ELIXIR is an intergovernmental organisation that brings together life science resources from across Europe. It operates the ELIXIR Data Platform that aims to fulfil the needs of the scientific community in both academic and industrial environments by providing open access to excellent data resources for effective data discovery, deposition and re-use. The ELIXIR platform provides a highly coordinated, scalable and connected data ecosystem with robust, long term sustainable data resources promoting open access as a core principle for publicly funded research.

ELIXIR Core Resources⁴ and Deposition Databases⁵ are a set of European data resources that ensure the long-term preservation of biological data of fundamental importance to the wider research community.

As outlined in the Data Management Plan (D2.1) it is recommended that for human cohort data (Generation R, ALSPAC, NFBC66/86, NESDA, Rotterdam, UK Biobank, NESDO), that approval is sought from owners of relevant sets for submission of appropriate cohort data into the European Genome-phenome archive (EGA)⁶, another ELIXIR Core Data Resource, respecting in-project data standards and complying with ethical requirements for each of the cohorts using the EGA's well established data access management protocols. Molecular sequence data from animal models and cell lines (subject to consent agreements) should be submitted to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)⁷, an ELIXIR Core Data Resource, for full open data access. Missing public mouse and cell line data of relevance will also be brokered into the ENA for DCC availability with the permission of data owners. We will provide support for submission of data to their relevant databases as well as their maintenance and retrieval, especially for WPs 5 and 6, around primary omics data, phenotyping data, histology images and relevant metadata.

Databases that are anticipated to be used in EarlyCause project are summarised in the table below.

Database	Core/Deposition	Data Type
European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	Core & Deposition	Molecular sequence data from animal models and cell lines
BioSamples⁸	Deposition	ELS exposure and mouse model stress descriptors
BioStudies⁹	Deposition	Mouse behavioural data
MetaboLights¹⁰	Deposition	Metabolic profiling data
BioImage Archive¹¹	Deposition	Image data
European Genome-phenome archive (EGA)	Core & Deposition	Personally identifiable genetic and phenotypic data resulting from biomedical research projects.

Table 1: Databases in the EarlyCause Platform.

2.2.1 Incorporating new data sets into the DCC

A Human data harmonization workshop was conducted on 20th May 2020, where it was discussed that it would be optimal to link databases to already existing Catalogues that include EarlyCause data like LifeCycle¹² and CLOSER¹³ and work on adding missing additional data.

Currently most cohort data are stored locally on servers in individual institution and concern was raised about submitting EarlyCause human cohort data to EGA.

EGA provides a controlled and secure access of sensitive human data that is restricted within national borders. The local federated EGA model¹⁴ allows the international connectivity of such data through its interoperable services, which accelerates research and health improvement of individuals across Europe. The federated EGA nodes of this model within each country ensures the access and sharing of metadata, with sequence data staying intact within the national borders.

It should be noted that UK Biobank has submitted array-based data, as well as exomes and genomes to EGA. Large microbiome projects such as MetaHIT¹⁵ and the integrative Human Microbiome Project¹⁶ have submitted anonymised microbiome data, which has been filtered to remove human reads, to ENA and its INSDC partner GenBank¹⁷, respectively.

For emerging data sets we will provide an autonomous rule-based system to detect newly published third-party data sets of relevance in the underlying archives and to make these available from the DCC. It will offer a service to partners through which they can “order” a relevant data set for inclusion in the DCC, should it not have been detected. All enquiries can be sent to ena-earlycause@ebi.ac.uk.

For project data types not yet in scope for ELIXIR archives, such as mouse behavioural data, we will exploit EarlyCause Consortium expertise to develop new utilities as required for manipulation and validation of data files for systematic representation of these in the DCC. We will, in addition, provide software tools and interfaces based on our existing web framework, spreadsheet handling tools, “Contextual Data Clearinghouse” and ontology management systems. For the reporting of metadata fields resulting from the project’s cohort data harmonisation efforts, to allow simple and visible layering of these descriptors upon cohort data to support search and integration which will ultimately be facilitated through the EarlyCause Cohort Browser.

A mouse/cell line workshop is planned to be held on mouse/cell line data in early October. This workshop aims to gather data specific requirements that would be relevant to be included in the DCC and ultimately on the EarlyCause Research Platform. Minimum reporting standards will also be determined as well as establishment of data formats, ontologies and standards during the workshop. EarlyCause human cohort researchers will also contribute to this workshop to ensure that human, mouse and cell line data are described in a way that allows data comparison and linkage.

2.3 Data Submission and Retrieval

Data can be submitted to the DCC using ENA's various submission routes namely:

- Interactive Submissions – Directly fill out web forms or download spreadsheets and fill them off-line and upload¹⁸.
- Programmatic Submissions – Prepare XML documents and send them to ENA using cURL command. Alternatively, the webin submissions portal can be used. A receipt XML with generated accessions and any validation or other errors will be provided¹⁸.
- Webin Command line interface (Webin-CLI) Submissions - The only route to submit assemblies and other analysis. A stand-alone, downloadable jar file run from a UNIX terminal or Windows command prompt. The command line is run specifying the type of data files being submitted, a manifest file describing experimental metadata and the Webin account login details. The data files are validated before uploading and submitting, after which the accession numbers will be generated. Unlike other submission routes, pre-upload of data files is not required¹⁸.

Dedicated support from the helpdesk team will be provided for submissions and a training workshop can be arranged if required.

The submission routes compatible for different types of data and metadata are tabulated below.

Data/Metadata	Interactive	Programmatic	Webin-CLI
Study	Y	N	Y
Sample	Y	N	Y
Read Data	Y	Y	Y
Genome Assembly	N	Y	N
Transcriptome Assembly	N	Y	N
Template Sequences	Y	Y	Y
Other Analyses	N	N	Y

Table 2: ENA Submission routes.

Once data is submitted, the ability to download submitted data is also made possible to the submitters. The DCC is designed to use the existing technology of the ENA that gives users access to a wide range of download applications for programmatic users through its APIs. For non-programmatic users, there are a range of graphical interface options, primarily the FTP client and Aspera¹⁹.

3 EarlyCause Research Platform

The EarlyCause Research Platform will bring all the elements of the DCC together, including the technical platform and Cohort Browser. It will allow data from large European cohorts to be integrated with animal models of both prenatal and postnatal stress, and cellular models in various tissues. There will be a project specific website which will allow a rich search and browse environment for the discovery and selection of appropriate data sets with relevant project protocols for further exploration. This will initially be available to EarlyCause partners to enable pre-publication access for a period of time to allow first interpretation of the data for publication purposes. Beyond the end of the project, data will be available to the research community under fully open or controlled access systems depending on the origin of the data.

The Platform will allow datasets to be “packaged” and assembled from search results and made available for retrieval. “Companion” web sites will be provided to offer focused reader access to relevant data from key EarlyCause publications. Finally, a webinar will be provided for training on the use of the Portal.

Figure 1: Overview of the EarlyCause centralised research platform, which will allow to upload, search and manage human and experimental data for investigating ELS-induced multi-morbidity.

4 Summary

The Data Coordination Centre brings together technical infrastructure through which data can be shared, securely managed and integrated. Data submitted to the recommended ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases in this report will ensure data and high-quality metadata which have permanent identifiers and comply with FAIR principles. This will ensure the sustainability of the data beyond the life of the project. A dedicated email address “ena-earlycause@ebi.ac.uk” will allow users to access assistance if required. The DCC will feed in to the EarlyCause Research Platform which will enable multidimensional data collection, integration and analysis to enable further research on early life stress and its psychological, cardiological and metabolic effects in later stages of life. A wide range of data and cohort studies will provide the opportunity to discover and select relevant models for further exploration, which in turn will contribute to further research and findings. Exploring and visualising the different pathways that are affected by ELS will make way to drug discoveries and drug target pathways for better treatment or prevention of PCM morbidities in future.

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